

FACTORS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF MUSICAL SKILLS OF HEARING-LIMITED CHILDREN

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Abstract. *The article talks about the impact of music on children with hearing impairment and how they feel music and how working with music affects their health. Also, what games can be used for children with hearing impairments.*

Keywords: *tempo, rhythm, dynamics, character, onomatopoeia, correction, aesthetic education.*

In recent years, the number of families with children in need of psychological-pedagogical support is increasing. Among them, we can include children with vision, hearing, forms of autism and other developmental disabilities.

As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoev said: "We are taking comprehensive measures to create an inclusive society where all citizens, including disabled people, have equal opportunities. On this basis, we have an important task before us. We aim to gradually move away from the medical model of defining disability, which has long been outdated. we will mobilize all our strength and capabilities so that he can be, do physical education and sports."

The attention paid by the state and society to disabled people, the changes being made are the impetus to improve the legislation that ensures the right of such children to education.

Nowadays, appropriate organizational work is being carried out to provide qualified psychological and pedagogical support to children with developmental disabilities from an early age. In new conditions, in practice, in special psychology and correctional pedagogy, in areas focused on working with children with disabilities, the possibilities of attracting all the resources that affect the development of such children in this direction are being determined. When working with such children, it is important to establish an emotional connection and to choose a form of education that is meaningfully understandable for him, to encourage activity. Specially organized music lessons can be considered as an effective means of psychological support for children with many developmental disabilities, as it provides a wide range of opportunities for the specialist to form sensorimotor, intellectual, and emotional skills.

Based on children's capabilities, the foundations of all-round development are laid in childhood, they are interested in various professions, and they quickly and easily memorize what they hear and remember it for many years. Currently, in the modern education system, teaching children with disabilities with the help of musical activities and games, taking into account their characteristics, teaching different types of musical performance, is one of the most important factors of education and upbringing. Musical education helps students to listen to music, to perform actions corresponding to music, to familiarize them with national culture, to expand their thoughts about the environment, and to develop their personality in all aspects.

In preschool children with hearing impairment (weak hearing), the development of music perception in children is carried out with the help of sound amplification equipment in the electromagnetic field. With the help of adults, children distinguish and react to changes in the

sound of music, the beginning and end of the melody, tempo (fast, slow), dynamics (loud, slow), character (calm, cheerful, march tempo). With the help of onomatopoeic games (imitating the sounds of cats, puppies, bears, and other animals), children try to sing and master sounds of different pitches, actively participate in singing with adults, sing songs. In the course of corrective work, children overcome difficulties in performing musical-rhythmic movements: they begin to feel musical instruments (tempo, rhythm, dynamics, character), learn to perform movement skills in accordance with music (walking, running, jumping, moving), in yins, they perform figurative movements and begin to harmonize their character with rhythmic and speech exercises made up of syllables.

Training on the development of musical movements is distinguished as a separate section and includes the formation of oral speech in children, development of memory and imagination, activation of cognitive activity, moral and aesthetic education, enrichment of the child's spiritual world, etc. In the process of performing musical exercises, children get rid of mental stress and get spiritual rest.

The general educational needs of hearing impaired children are fulfilled in the process of musical education. Currently, in music lessons in general education schools, in many cases, songs are organized by audio materials, instrumental music, the study of its form and content are neglected.

Acquiring educational qualifications requires the use of special tools and certain special methods. Thanks to this, the pedagogical process will have a corrective direction.

Musical education for hearing impaired children contributes to the development of their ability to concentrate, emotional perception, and the ability to independently coordinate musical movements, just like healthy children. In the perception of music, hearing-impaired children learn to develop residual hearing and perceive the tempo, rhythm, and volume of music with special, corrective work. It helps children to master the rhythmic-intonation aspect of speech. Hearing impaired children express their attitude towards music when they listen to music over and over again. They get acquainted with musical genres (march, dance, song), instrumental performance, vocal performance (choir, soloist, symphony orchestra, instruments, classical and folk music works). they start getting to know their names.

Musical training in hearing impaired children helps to develop the following needs;

- Ways to develop the skills of perception of oral speech by different sensors (auditory-visual, that is, reading and listening from the lips of the speaker)
- Development of oral speech as a means of communication;
- Development of speech pronunciation

The development of such needs helps a person to successfully adapt to society. Music and musical activities have a positive effect not only on hearing impaired children, but also on children with other developmental disabilities. Properly selected music has the properties of calming the human body, relieving fatigue, improving mood and sleep.

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